

Kinetic-mechanistic study of Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation of 3,5-xylylidine

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Abstract : The kinetics of the Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation of 3,5-xylylidine (3,5-DMA) in acetone-water medium has been followed by monitoring the increase in the absorbance of reaction intermediate. Reaction is first order in reactants and catalyst each. A decrease in dielectric constant of the medium results in decrease in the rate of reaction. Free radical scavengers do not affect the reaction rate. One mol of 3,5-DMA reacts with two moles of periodate during the initial part of reaction. The main reaction product is 2,6-dimethyl-*p*-benzoquinone. The values of thermodynamic parameters are : $\Delta E = 22.98 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $A = 1.10 \times 10^9 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -151.44 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 67.42 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta H^\ddagger = 20.40 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. Under pseudo-first order conditions, $[\text{IO}_4^-] \gg [3,5\text{-DMA}]$, the rate law is given by :

$$1/k_{\text{cat}} = (K_2/kK_3K_4 [\text{H}^+]) + \{(K_w + K_bK_2)/kK_3K_4K_w\} + K_b[\text{H}^+]/kK_3K_4K_w$$

where kK_3K_4 is the empirical composite rate constant, K_w is ionic product of water, K_2 is acid dissociation constant of H_4IO_6^- and K_b is base dissociation constant of 3,5-DMA. In agreement with the rate law the $1/k_{\text{cat}}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ plot passes through the minimum. Detailed molecular mechanism is given.

Keywords : Kinetics, Mn^{II}, periodate, 3,5-xylylidine, 2,6-dimethyl-*p*-benzoquinone.

Introduction

There are few reports available on the kinetic-mechanistic studies of the uncatalysed non-Malapradian periodate oxidation of aromatic amines¹⁻⁹. Some of the recent reports include the Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation of 2,4-xylylidine¹⁰, 2,6-xylylidine¹¹, *N*-methylaniline¹², *p*-toluidine¹³, 4-chloro, 2-methyl aniline¹⁴ and 5-chloro, 2-methyl aniline³⁰. The studies are important as these can be used in developing methods for detection and treatment of the aromatic amines – the chemicals enlisted as toxic¹⁵. In present communication, the kinetic-mechanistic studies on Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation of 3,5-xylylidine (3,5-DMA) in acetone-water medium are being presented and discussed.

Experimental

Sodium metaperiodate (Loba Chemie), 3,5-DMA (Aldrich), acetone (E. Merck), manganese sulphate monohydrate (Aldrich) and all other chemicals of analytical reagent/guaranteed reagent grade were used after redis-

tillation/recrystallization. Triply distilled water was used for preparation of the solutions. Thiel, Schultz and Koch buffer¹⁶ was used for maintaining the pH.

On mixing the reactants, the solution becomes violet which later changes to orange colour. On keeping for long time, it finally gives the product. These observations indicate the formation of more than one intermediate prior to the formation of final reaction product. The UV-Vis spectra of IO_4^- , 3,5-DMA and Mn^{II} indicated these to show no absorption in visible region. Hence, for following the kinetics the absorbance changes were recorded on Shimadzu double beam spectrophotometer (UV-2450) having high precision thermostatic control, at 490 nm (at which only the intermediate absorbs). Absorption maxima was not found to change with change in time under experimental conditions as shown by the rapid scan of the solution (Fig. 1).

Excess of oxidant was mixed with substrate and catalyst and set aside for 24 h. The reaction mixture was filtered after it and the filtrate was extracted with petro-

Fig. 1. UV-Vis rapid scan at $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 8.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[3,5\text{-DMA}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 5.0$, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = 7.28 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, acetone = 5.0% (v/v), Temp. = $35.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

leum ether (40–60 $^\circ\text{C}$). The extract was evaporated at room temperature. From residue, a yellow compound and a brown compound were separated by TLC with following para-meters fixed by hit and trial : plate thickness = 0.5 mm, adsorbent = silica gel 'G', eluent = chloroform : acetone : benzene (10 : 05 : 85), time for development = 35 min. The remaining part of the filtrate might be containing other products of this reaction that could not be separated and identified. Yellow coloured compound was collected by preparatory TLC while brown coloured compound, being a minor component, could not be collected in sufficient amount. The yellow coloured compound was recrystallised in petroleum ether and characterized as 2,6-dimethyl-*p*-benzoquinone on the basis of positive test for quinone¹⁷, melting point 70 $^\circ\text{C}$ (sublimes) (literature

value¹⁸ 72–73 $^\circ\text{C}$), and UV spectrum (in CHCl_3) giving absorption maxima at 360, 320 and 435 nm (literature values¹⁹ 255, 319 and 429 nm). The IR spectrum of this compound (in KBr) showed the presence of bands at 1665 cm^{-1} (s) (indicating the presence of C=O on 1,4-benzoquinone pattern with the possibility that the position of this band got lowered due to +I effect of methyl group²⁰), 3260 cm^{-1} (s) (may be due to overtones of C=O stretch as the frequency is about twice that of C=O stretch) and 2725 cm^{-1} (s) (due to isolated C–H stretching²¹). Further, the bands were obtained at 1380 cm^{-1} (s) and 1350 cm^{-1} (s) (may be due to C=C ring stretch), 1200 cm^{-1} (m) and 1100 cm^{-1} (m) (may be due to in-plane C–H bending) and the bands at 710 cm^{-1} (m) and 660 cm^{-1} (m) (due to out-of-plane C=C bending mode). On the basis

of these studies, the product may be 2,6-dimethyl-*p*-benzoquinone.

Results

Reaction stoichiometry :

Unreacted periodate was estimated iodimetrically. $\log(a-x)$ versus time plot (where $a-x$ is the concentration of unreacted periodate) followed the pseudo-first order behaviour upto a point after which the inflexion was obtained. It was taken as the point corresponding to the completion of first stage of reaction for which the kinetics was studied. It was found that 1 mol of 3,5-DMA consumes 2 moles of periodate for initial stage of the reaction as given below.

Another molecule of periodate may react in later stages of the reaction to give other reaction products.

Rate law :

The kinetics was studied under pseudo order conditions by keeping periodate concentration in excess. Guggenheim's method was used for evaluation of pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} . Under these conditions, the kinetics was defined by the rate law (2).

$$d[C]/dt = k_{\text{cat}} [3,5\text{-DMA}]_0 [\text{IO}_4^-]_0 [\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] \quad (2)$$

where $k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{cat}} [\text{IO}_4^-]_0 [\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$ and k_{cat} is the rate constant for Mn^{II} catalysed pathway. $[\text{IO}_4^-]_0$ and $[3,5\text{-DMA}]_0$ represent the initial or total concentration of periodate and substrate. In the absence of Mn^{II}, no significant reaction occurred. The values of k_{cat} obtained for different $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$, $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ and $[3,5\text{-DMA}]$ are seen to be in good agreement and consistent with the rate law eq. (2).

Effect of various factors :

As the reacting species are differently protonated, it was considered necessary to study the effect of pH on the reaction rate and hence, the reaction was studied in the pH range 4.5 to 7.5. $1/k_{\text{cat}}$ vs pH plot indicates a minimum at pH = 6.5 (Fig. 2). Since the substrate is soluble only in acetone-water binary mixture, the kinetics had been studied in 5.0% (v/v) acetone-water mixtures. Because of this, it became necessary to examine the effect

Fig. 2. $1/k_{\text{cat}}$ vs pH plot at $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 8.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, $[3,5\text{-DMA}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = 7.28 \times 10^{-6}$ mol dm⁻³, acetone = 5.0% (v/v), $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 490$ nm, Temp. = 35.0 ± 0.1 °C.

of varying proportion of acetone in binary reaction mixtures on reaction rate. An increase in the acetone (5.0–20.0%) i.e. a decrease in dielectric constant (D) of the medium, led to a decrease in rate. Graphical plots between k_{cat} and $1/D$, were found to be straight line with negative slope. Further, free radical scavengers, viz. acrylamide and allyl alcohol had no effect on the reaction rate, indicating thereby, no involvement of free radicals in the reaction.

The rate constants were determined at four different temperatures (30.0 to 45.0 °C) and the values of different thermodynamic parameters viz. activation energy (ΔE), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger), Arrhenius frequency factor (A), free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) and enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) were found. The mean values are $\Delta E = 22.98$ kJ mol⁻¹, $A = 1.10 \times 10^9$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹; $\Delta S^\ddagger = -151.44$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 67.42$ kJ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta H^\ddagger = 20.40$ kJ mol⁻¹. The value of ΔG^\ddagger was temperature dependent. A high negative value of ΔS^\ddagger is suggestive of solvent interactions and the probability that the transition state may be solvated. Small value of activation energy is characteristic of catalyzed reaction. Statistical analysis confirmed that the standard errors of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger correlate and lead to the centre of temperature range used, as given by the relation²² : $T_{\text{av}} = \sigma(\Delta H^\ddagger)/\sigma(\Delta S^\ddagger)$.

Discussion

Preliminary observations indicate the formation of the colored intermediate on a time scale of minutes and that of the final product on a time scale of hours. The overall reaction appears to involve several steps and possibly several transient intermediates, in addition to comparatively stable one C₄, during the oxidation of 3,5-DMA into benzoquinone. Further, the kinetic order of one in periodate against the requirement of two periodate molecules for each 3,5-DMA molecule in the stoichiometry [eq. (1)] requires the involvement of only one periodate in the rate determining step and second IO₄⁻ ion to be consumed in a fast step leading to the formation of an intermediate. Since the concentration of intermediate increases continuously with time and reaches a limiting value, its concentration can not be in steady state. Next important feature is the 1/k_{cat} versus pH plot (Fig. 2), which indicates the presence of at least three differently reactive species of reactant (which is periodate in this system) in the pH region chosen for study²³. Finally, the observation that free radical scavengers have no effect on reaction rate rules out the involvement of free radicals in the oxidation mechanism. The high negative value of entropy of activation supports the involvement of solvation effects in this reaction as given in the proposed molecular mechanism (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

While proposing a suitable mechanism for the reaction under study, the speciation of 3,5-DMA and periodate should be considered. In aqueous solutions, periodate is transformed into the three forms in water including ortho-periodic acid²⁴ with equilibria and dissociation constants^{25,26} given below :

The value of K_1 indicates that in the pH range 4.5–9.5 species H₅IO₆ shall be practically non-existent and hence only species H₄IO₆⁻ and H₃IO₆²⁻ need be considered for explaining observed pH-dependence. Based on this premise, the equilibrium or free concentration of H₄IO₆⁻, [H₄IO₆⁻] shall be related to the total periodate concentration [IO₄⁻]₀ by eq. (5).

$$[\text{H}_4\text{IO}_6^-] = [\text{IO}_4^-]_0 [\text{H}^+] / ([\text{H}^+] + K_2) \quad (5)$$

In the reaction mechanism proposed later, species H₄IO₆⁻ has been considered reactive.

In aqueous solution, 3,5-DMA, undergoes the following acid-base equilibrium with $K_b^{27} = 5.82 \times 10^{-10}$.

Since in the studied pH-range, both CH₃CH₃C₆H₄NH₂ and CH₃CH₃C₆H₄N⁺H₃ exist, these species have been taken into account. From equilibrium (6), the equilibrium or free concentration of amine, [3,5-DMA], is given by eq. (7).

$$[\text{3,5-DMA}] = [\text{3,5-DMA}]_0 [\text{OH}^-] / \{[\text{OH}^-] + K_b\} \quad (7)$$

where [3,5-DMA]₀ is the total concentration of CH₃CH₃-C₆H₄NH₂.

By assuming 3,5-DMA and H₄IO₆⁻ to be reactive species. On this basis to explain the observed kinetics, rate law [eq. (2)], and pH-dependence, the following mechanism is proposed.

In steps (6-9), [C₁], [C₂], [C₃] and [C₄] are intermediates, out of which [C₄] appears to undergo very slow reorganization/hydrolysis to yield the reaction product, C₅.

The formation of intermediates [C₁] and [C₂] in a rapid step having low values of equilibrium constants, K₃ and K₄, is assumed in the proposed gross mechanism. In the detailed mechanism (Scheme 1), the catalytic role of Mn²⁺

appears to be due to the formation of a ternary complex, [(3,5-DMA)Mn(H₄IO₆)]⁺, in which electron transfer takes place through Mn. Further the proposed gross mechanism matches the kinetic and product studies, as given in Scheme 1. The formation of a charged intermediate complex C₂ by the attack of IO₄⁻ on the nitrogen of anilino group and stabilization of positive charge on nitrogen of this group, has already been established and supported by LFER studies for the uncatalyzed periodate oxidation of aromatic amines^{5,6,28} and for Mn^{II} catalysed periodate oxidation of same²⁹. In addition, a high negative value of entropy of activation and the effect of dielectric constant on the reaction rate support the involvement of solvation effects in this reaction.

Table 1. Effect of variation of concentration of reactants, [Mn^{II}], pH and dielectric constant on the reaction rate at temperature = 35.0 ± 0.1 °C

[NaIO ₄] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	[3,5-DMA] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	Mn ^{II} × 10 ⁶ (mol dm ⁻³)	Acetone % (v/v)	pH	k _{obs} × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	k _{cat} × 10 ⁻⁵ (dm ⁶ mol ⁻² s ⁻¹)
50.0	2.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	4.95	1.36
60.0	2.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	5.99	1.37
70.0	2.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	7.02	1.38
80.0	2.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	8.06	1.38
90.0	2.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	9.10	1.39
100.0	2.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	10.13	1.39
80.0	2.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	8.06	1.38
80.0	3.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	8.41	1.44
80.0	4.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	8.52	1.46
80.0	5.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	8.75	1.50
80.0	6.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	8.87	1.52
80.0	7.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	8.98	1.54
80.0	2.0	3.28	5.0	5.0	3.45	1.32
80.0	2.0	5.28	5.0	5.0	5.64	1.34
80.0	2.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	8.06	1.38
80.0	2.0	9.28	5.0	5.0	10.25	1.38
2.0	80.0	7.28	5.0	4.5	1.52	0.26
2.0	80.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	2.65	0.46
2.0	80.0	7.28	5.0	5.5	3.46	0.59
2.0	80.0	7.28	5.0	6.0	4.15	0.71
2.0	80.0	7.28	5.0	6.5	4.47	0.77
2.0	80.0	7.28	5.0	7.0	4.32	0.74
2.0	80.0	7.28	5.0	7.5	3.99	0.69
80.0	2.0	7.28	5.0	5.0	8.06	1.38
80.0	2.0	7.28	10.0	5.0	5.99	1.03
80.0	2.0	7.28	15.0	5.0	3.57	0.61
80.0	2.0	7.28	20.0	5.0	1.96	0.34

The proposed mechanism (8–11) leads to the rate law (13).

$$d[C_4]/dt = kK_3K_4[Mn^{II}][H_4IO_6^-][3,5-DMA] \quad (13)$$

On substituting the values of concentrations of the reactive species [3,5-DMA] and $[H_4IO_6^-]$ from eqs. (5) and (7) in eq. (13), and taking $H_4IO_6^-$ as IO_4^- for simplicity²⁶, the complete rate law including $[H^+]$ -dependence becomes :

$$d[C]/dt = kK_3K_4[Mn^{II}]\{([3,5-DMA]_0[OH^-]/([OH^-] + K_b))\} \{([IO_4^-]_0[H^+]/(K_2 + [H^+]))\} \quad (14)$$

On replacing the term, $[OH^-][H^+]$, by K_w in numerator, and $[OH^-]$ by $K_w/[H^+]$ in denominator, and on rearranging, the eq. (14) becomes eq. (15).

$$d[C]/dt = kK_3K_4[Mn^{II}]K_w[3,5-DMA]_0[IO_4^-]_0[H^+]/\{K_2K_w + (K_w + K_bK_2)[H^+] + K_b[H^+]^2\} \quad (15)$$

On comparing eqs. (2) and (15), we get

$$k_{cat} = kK_3K_4K_w[H^+]/\{K_2K_w + (K_w + K_bK_2)[H^+] + K_b[H^+]^2\} \quad (16)$$

Eq. (16) on rearranging becomes eq. (17).

$$1/k_{cat} = (K_2/kK_3K_4[H^+]) + \{(K_w + K_bK_2)/kK_3K_4K_w\} + K_b[H^+]/kK_3K_4K_w \quad (17)$$

The k_{cat} and pH data were fitted to eq. (17). All experimental k_{cat} values are in good agreement with the calculated values as shown in Table 2. Thus, eq. (17) satisfactorily explains the observed kinetics in all pH range 4.5 to 7.5.

On differentiating $1/k_{cat}$ with respect to $[H^+]$ in, we get the values of $d^2[1/k_{cat}]/d[H^+]^2$. The value of second derivative is found to be positive showing the plot of $1/k_{cat}$ versus $[H^+]$ or pH to pass through a minimum.

Table 2. Calculated and observed values of rate constants at different pH

pH	$k_{cat} \times 10^{-5}$ (Obsd.)	$k_{cat} \times 10^{-5}$ (Calcd.)
4.5	0.26	0.27
5.0	0.46	0.50
5.5	0.59	0.63
6.0	0.71	0.71
6.5	0.77	0.73
7.0	0.74	0.72
7.5	0.69	0.66

Fig. 2 presents same observation. Further, on setting $d[1/k_{cat}]/d[H^+]$ equal to zero for obtaining hydrogen ion concentration at which the $1/k_{cat}$ vs $[H^+]$ profile will pass through minimum, we obtain,

$$[H^+]_{min} = (K_2K_w/K_b)^{1/2} \quad (16)$$

On substituting the values of K_2 , K_w and K_b , we get,

$$[H^+]_{min} = 2.73 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

It is noteworthy that the calculated value of $[H^+]_{min}$ is in good agreement with the experimental value of $[H^+]_{min}$ of $3.16 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ obtained from $1/k_{cat}$ versus pH plot (Fig. 2) and this provides good support to the proposed mechanism.

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